

EDITORIAL

On December 13, 2002, the founding assembly of the International Association of Non-Profit Public Marketing (AIMNP) took place in Spain. The idea of creating the association was formulated in April of that year during the Public and Non-Profit Marketing Conference in the city of León, Spain. These conferences emerged at the initiative of a small group of Spanish and Portuguese academics who, in 2001, understood the need to promote the development of social, public and non-profit marketing as a research field. After the founding assembly, the application for the association's entry into the Registry of Associations of Spain was submitted, and on April 16, 2003, that application was approved. This new issue of Responsibility and Sustainability coincides with the 20th anniversary of the formal start of AIMNP's activities.

Those first Public and Non-Profit Marketing Conferences became the association's annual international congress, whose 22nd edition will take place this year under the slogan "Cultural values in non-business marketing." Our colleagues from Hungary will be organizing this congress at the University of Pannonia between July 5 and 7. Initially, AIMNP grew in Spain and Portugal, but quickly began to incorporate colleagues from various European countries, South Africa, Australia, and Latin America. In particular, AIMNP expanded in several Eastern European countries, such as Hungary, Romania, Croatia, Lithuania, among others. During these years, the association has operated as a networking platform for academics working on issues related to social marketing, social responsibility, and sustainability, which has led to multiple international research projects.

In 2019, AIMNP held its first Latin American congress in Córdoba, Argentina. During this congress, a working team was created that later took charge of organizing the Latin American section of the association. This team organized the three following congresses in Uruguay (2020, online), Venezuela (2021, online), and Peru (2022, hybrid format). Currently, they are working on the organization of the fifth congress, which will take place in Cali, Colombia, on September 28 and 29 (hybrid format). In addition to organizing its annual congress, the Latin American section of AIMNP took over the publication of Responsibility and Sustainability, which had been founded and managed by a group of colleagues from the University of León, Spain, but had ceased publication in 2017. The first issue of this second period was published in 2020.

As part of the celebrations for the 20th anniversary of the association, the team leading the Latin American section (AIMNP-LATAM) has begun implementing various actions aimed at increasing its presence in all countries in the region. The central purpose of AIMNP-LATAM is to promote research in the broad spectrum of topics related to social marketing, organizational social responsibility, and sustainability. In pursuit of this goal, the annual Latin American congress is held, Responsibility and Sustainability is published, and networks of researchers are being built.

The congress aims to serve as a space for reflection and sharing research among our members and other colleagues. In particular, we intend for the congress to help build networks of researchers, and for teams to emerge from these networks that design and implement research on common topics in our region's countries. The editorial policies of the journal are aimed at creating a space where colleagues from the region can publish their research papers. In particular, the journal focuses on early-career researchers who may find it challenging to access journals to publish their articles. In addition to rigorously evaluating their work, we provide methodological guidance to help them improve the quality of their articles. It is also worth noting that under the impetus of

AIMNP-LATAM, teams of researchers from different countries have been created. Some of these teams are already implementing international research, others have published articles in scientific journals, and others have presented papers at international conferences.

Joining AIMNP is an opportunity for the professional growth of Latin American academics. Participation in the association provides opportunities to participate in international research projects, adapt research already carried out by colleagues from other countries, share the results of their research work in our congresses, and publish articles. In this regard, we announce here that starting this year, Responsibility and Sustainability will begin publishing special issues that will include articles presented at the three annual AIMNP congresses: the international, the Latin American, and the case study congress (which takes place in December).

If you have participated in our congresses, published in Responsibility and Sustainability, cited any of the articles published on our website, or if you have simply accessed it to stay informed, consider yourself invited to join AIMNP.

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Editors